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ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Database and digital collection managers Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Monitor Status, Access

Data collected in Real Time

Challenges in Monitoring Status, Access and Integrity

Database and digital collection managers Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

Database and digital collection managers Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

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Database and digital collection managers
3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

Database and digital collection managers
Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

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Database and digital collection managers

Cross-analysis insights

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TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	High-resolution images	3D models (e.g., point clouds, meshes)	Audio and video materials (e.g., oral histories, video archives)	Scientific data (e.g., analysis reports, lab data)	Environmental monitoring data	Metadata and cataloguing records	Archival documentation (e.g., administrative records, conservation logs)	GIS or geospatial data	Linked Open Data
Collection management systems (e.g., TMS, MuseumPlus, Adlib)	2	1	2	3	0	4	3	3	3
Digital asset management systems (e.g., ResourceSpace, Preservica)	0	1	0	3	0	2	1	2	2
Databases or relational database tools (e.g., MySQL, PostgreSQL, FileMaker)	12	7	5	11	2	16	7	15	11
Metadata editing or cataloguing tools (e.g., Oxygen XML, OpenRefine)	7	4	3	9	0	11	4	9	10
Linked data / semantic web tools (e.g., RDF editors, SPARQL endpoints)	8	6	4	12	1	13	5	11	13
Interoperability or harvesting platforms (e.g., OAI-PMH, Europeana tools)	6	3	4	7	0	9	4	7	7
I manage collections but am not directly involved in digitization workflows	1	2	1	1	1	2	0	1	1

TECHNOLOGIES × REAL-TIME DATA	Real-time ingestion (e.g., sensor feeds, automated pipelines)	Batch imports at scheduled intervals	Manual input or uploads as needed	A mix of the above	I'm not sure / Not applicable
Collection management systems (e.g., TMS, MuseumPlus, Adlib)	0	2	2	0	0
Digital asset management systems (e.g., ResourceSpace, Preservica)	0	0	1	2	0
Databases or relational database tools (e.g., MySQL, PostgreSQL, FileMaker)	1	6	5	7	1
Metadata editing or cataloguing tools (e.g., Oxygen XML, OpenRefine)	1	5	2	5	0
Linked data / semantic web tools (e.g., RDF editors, SPARQL endpoints)	1	6	2	7	1
Interoperability or harvesting platforms (e.g., OAI-PMH, Europeana tools)	1	4	1	4	0
I manage collections but am not directly involved in digitization workflows	1	1	0	2	0

MONITORING TOOLS × MONITORING CHALLENGES	Heterogeneity of data formats and sources	Lack of standardized metadata or taxonomies	Limited tools for ensuring data consistency and accuracy	Integration difficulties with external platforms or databases	Inadequate staff capacity or training	High cost of specialized infrastructure/software	I do not experience major challenges
Digital repository management systems with monitoring features	8	6	4	7	4	3	1
Metadata auditing and validation tools	5	4	5	6	6	3	0
User access monitoring platforms	3	3	1	1	2	1	0
File integrity or preservation monitoring tools	3	3	1	2	3	2	0
I do not use digital tools for monitoring	6	4	2	3	4	1	4

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	Structured metadata (e.g., XML, JSON, RDF)	Relational databases (e.g., MySQL, PostgreSQL)	Unstructured files (e.g., Word, TIFF, PDF, CSV)	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, gTF, point clouds)	Multimedia formats (e.g., JPEG, MP4, WAV)	Linked Open Data (e.g., RDF, JSON-LD, SKOS)	Proprietary formats (e.g., from specialized software)
High-resolution images	11	11	8	5	11	6	4
3D models (e.g., point clouds, meshes)	7	9	4	6	7	4	3
Audio and video materials (e.g., oral histories, video archives)	5	4	5	3	7	2	2
Scientific data (e.g., analysis reports, lab data)	13	11	10	4	8	8	5
Environmental monitoring data	3	1	0	0	1	1	0
Metadata and cataloguing records	15	14	12	4	11	10	4
Archival documentation (e.g., administrative records, conservation logs)	7	7	5	3	6	3	4
GIS or geospatial data	14	14	9	5	10	9	6
Linked Open Data	14	8	9	1	6	11	3

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING DIFFICULTIES	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats	Legal or institutional restrictions	Lack of adequate infrastructure for data sharing	Concerns about intellectual property and data misuse	Lack of time or staff to prepare data for reuse	I have no difficulties in sharing data
Yes, platforms internal to my institution	9	9	9	6	9	1
Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., Europeana)	8	6	8	3	6	0
No, but I'd be interested in using them	3	3	5	3	5	0
No, I don't see their usefulness	0	0	0	0	0	0

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of interoperability between systems or standards	Difficulty aligning legacy data with current platforms	Limited resources for integration or migration	Fragmentation across departments or responsibilities	Inadequate training or support for staff	No significant challenges
Yes, frequently	4	1	4	2	3	1
Yes, occasionally	8	6	6	5	7	2
No, but I would be interested	5	3	3	3	3	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	2	1	1	1	1

3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Integration and visualization of heterogeneous data sources	Monitoring of data quality and system performance	Simulation of metadata workflows and data curation scenarios	Long-term preservation planning and risk analysis	Enhancing accessibility and reuse of cultural data	Collaboration between institutions through shared Digital Twin frameworks	I don't see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	5	2	2	4	6	3	0
Yes, occasionally	5	3	2	4	9	6	1
No, but I would be interested	2	2	0	1	3	4	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	2	2	1	2	1	2	1

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of interoperability between systems or standards	Difficulty aligning legacy data with current platforms	Limited resources for integration or migration	Fragmentation across departments or responsibilities	Inadequate training or support for staff	No significant challenges
Yes, frequently	3	1	2	2	2	1
Yes, occasionally	3	2	1	1	2	0
No, but I would be interested	10	6	9	7	8	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	2	3	2	1	2	3

SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN SUPPORT	Aggregation and visualization of multi-source collection data	Simulations of metadata use, reuse, or enrichment	Suggestions for preservation or curation strategies	Alerts and notifications on data quality or inconsistencies	Integration with semantic web or linked open data platforms	Collaboration between institutions to develop and share interoperable models
Yes, frequently	2	2	2	3	3	3
Yes, occasionally	1	0	2	2	1	2
No, but I would be interested	10	6	8	9	8	7
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	4	4	2	2	3	3